

Applications of Kushare Integral Transform in Mechanics

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Abstract:- Integral transform plays important role in various fields. Recently, Kushare, Takate and Patil introduced Kushare transform in 2021. Many researchers used this transform for solving various problems. In this paper we use Kushare transform for solving problems from mechanics. We use it to simple harmonic motion.

Keywords:- Integral transform, Kushare transform, Simple Harmonic Motion.

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, integral transforms are one of the most useful and simple mathematical technique for obtaining the solutions of advance problems occurred in many fields like science, Engineering, technology, commerce and economics. To provide exact solution of problem without lengthy calculations is the important feature of integral transforms.

Due to this important feature of the integral transforms many researchers are attracted to this field and are engaged in introducing various integral transforms. Recently, Kushare and Patil [1] introduced new integral transform called as Kushare transform for solving differential equations in time domain. Further, Savita Khakale and Dinkar Patil [2] introduced Soham transform in November 2021. As researchers are interested in introducing the new integral transforms at the same time they are also interested in applying the transforms to various fields, various equations in different domain. In January 2022, Sanap and Patil [3] used Kushare transform for obtaining the solution of the problems on Newton's law of Cooling.

In April 2022 D. P. Patil, et al [4] used Kushare transform for solving the problems on population growth and decay. D.P. Patil [5] also used Sawi transform in Bessel functions. Further, Patil [6] evaluate improper integrals by using Sawi transform of error functions. Laplace transforms and Shehu transforms are used in chemical sciences by Patil [7]. Dinkar Patil [8] used Sawi transform and its convolution theorem for solving wave equation. Using Mahgoub transform, parabolic boundary value problems are solved by D.P. Patil [9].

D .P. Patil [10] used double Laplace and double Sumudu transforms to obtain the solution of wave equation. Further Dr. Patil [11] also obtained dualities between double integral transforms. Kandalkar, Gatkal and Patil [12] solved the system of differential equations using Kushare transform. D. P. Patil [13] used Aboodh and Mahgoub transforms to solve boundary value problems of the system

of ordinary differential equations. Double Mahgoub transformed is used by Patil [14] to solve parabolic boundary value problems.

Laplace, Sumudu, Aboodh, Elazki and Mahagoub transforms are compared and used it for solving boundary value problems by Dinkar Patil [15]. D. P. Patil et al [16] obtained solution of Volterra Integral equations of first kind by using Emad-Sara transform. Futher Patil with Tile and Shinde [17] used Anuj transform for solving Volterra integral equations of first kind. Rathi sisters and D. P. Patil [18] solved system of differential equations by using Soham transform. Vispute, Jadhav and Patil [19] used Emad Sara transform for solving telegraph equation. Kandalkar, Zankar and Patil [20] evaluate the improper integrals by using general integral transform of error function. Dinkar Patil, Prerana Thakare and Prajakta Patil [21] obtained the solution of parabolic boundary value problems by using double general integral transform. Dinkar Patil used Emad-Falih transform for solving problems based on Newton's law of cooling [22].

D. P. Patil et al [23] used Soham transform to obtain the solution of Newton's law of cooling. Dinkar Patil et al [24] used HY integral transform for handling growth and Decay problems, D. P. Patil et al used HY integral transform for Newton's law of cooling [25]. D. P. Patil et al [26] used Emad-Falih transform for general solution of telegraph equation. Dinkar Patil et al [27] introduced double kushare transform. Recently, D. P. Patil et al [28] solved population growth and decay problems by using Emad Sara transform. Alenzi transform is used in population growth and decay problems by Patil et al [29]. Thete, et al [30] used Emad Falih transform for handling growth and decay problems. Nikam, Patil et al [31] used, Kushare transform of error functions in evaluating improper integrals.

Wagh sisters and Patil used Kushare [32] and Soham [33] transform in chemical Sciences. Malpani, Shinde and Patil [34] used Convolution theorem for Kushare transform and applications in convolution type Volterra integral equations of first kind. Raundal and Patil [35] used double general integral transform for solving boundary value problems in partial differential equations. Rahane, Derle and Patil [36] developed generalized double rangaig integral transform.

Shinde, et al [37] used Kushare transform is used for solving Volterra Integro-Differential equations of first kind. Kandekar et al [38] used new general integral equation to solve Abel's integral equations. Pardeshi, Shaikh and Patil [39] used Kharrat Toma transform for solving population growth and decay problems. Patil et al [40] used Kushare

transform for evaluating integrals containing Bessel’s functions. Thakare and Patil [41] used general integral transform for solving mathematical models from health sciences. Rathi sisters used Soham transform for analysis of impulsive response of Mechanical and Electrical oscillators with Patil [42]. Patil [43] used KKAT transform for solving growth and decay problems. Suryawanshi et al [44] used Soham transform for solving models in health sciences and biotechnology.

We organize this paper as follows. Introduction is included in section one. Second section is devoted for preliminary concepts. Kushare transform is used to the problems in mechanics in third section.

B. Kushare transform of some functions:

In this section we state formulae of some elementary functions

SR. NO	FUNCTION	KUSHARE TRANSFORM
1	1	$\frac{1}{v^{\alpha-1}} = s(v)$
2	t^n	$\frac{n+1}{v^{\alpha(n+1)-1}}$
3	e^{at}	$\frac{v}{v^\alpha - a}$
4	$\sin(at)$	$\frac{av}{(v^{2a} + a^2)}$
5	$\cos(at)$	$\frac{v^{\alpha+1}}{(v^{2a} + a^2)}$

Table 1: Kushare transform of some functions

C. Kushare transform of derivative:

If $s(v)$ is Kushare transform of function $f(t)$ then

- $K[f'(t)] = v^\alpha s(v) - vf(0)$
- $K[f''(t)] = v^{2\alpha} s(v) - v^{\alpha+1} f(0) - vf'(0)$
- $3. K[f^n(t)] = v^{na} s(v) - v \sum_{k=0}^{n-1} v^{\alpha(n-k-1)} f^k(0)$

III. APPLICATIONS OF KUSHARE TRANSFORM TO MECHANICS

In this section we use Kushare transform to solve problems from mechanics.

➤ **Simple Harmonic Motion**

We consider a particle having mass m , which execute the simple harmonic motion. Let x be the displacement of the particle from the mean position at any time t . The differential equation describing the motion of the particle at time t is given by

$$x''(t) + \omega^2 x = 0, \omega^2 = k/m$$

We apply Kushare transform to find the displacement of this particle at any time t .

Assume that at $t = 0$ and $x(0) = 0, x'(0) = 1$

Solution: Consider the second order differential equation

$$x''(t) + \omega^2 x = 0$$

Applying Kushare integral

$$K[x''(t)] + \omega^2 K(x) = 0$$

$$v^{2\alpha} s(v) - v^{\alpha+1} x(0) - vx'(0) + \omega^2 s(v) = 0$$

II. PRELIMINARY

In this section we state some preliminary concepts required, i.e. definition, formulae and theorems from Kushare transform.

A. Definition of Kushare integral transform:

$$A = \left\{ f(t): \exists M, \tau_1 \tau_2 > 0, |f| < (t) M e^{\frac{|t|}{\tau_j}}, \text{ if } t \in (-1)^j * [0, \infty) \right\}$$

$$K[f(t)] = S(v) = v \int_0^\infty f(t) e^{-tv^\alpha} dt, t \geq 0, \tau_1 \leq v \leq \tau_2$$

$$(v^{2\alpha} + \omega^2)s(v) - 0 - v = 0$$

$$s(v) = \frac{v}{(v^{2\alpha} + \omega^2)}$$

Taking inverse on both side

$$K^{-1}[s(v)] = K^{-1}\left[\frac{v}{(v^{2\alpha} + \omega^2)}\right]$$

$$x(t) = \frac{\sin \omega t}{\omega}$$

That is $x(t) = \sqrt{\frac{m}{k}} \sin \sqrt{\frac{k}{m}} t$

It is the required displacement of the particle.

- Let a body A of mass 1 gram moves on -axis. It is attracted towards the origin 0 with a force equals to 4x. Also, assume that initially it is at rest when x = 5 then; determine its position by considering no any other forces acting on it.

Figure 1: Motion of the body along x axis

- Solution:** See above figure number 1,

For $x > 0$ the net force towards left is given by $-4x$, while

For $x < 0$ the net force towards right is given by $-4x$.

Thus, for both cases, the net force is equal to $-4x$.

By Newton’s second law of motion: Mass * acceleration = net force

Therefore we can obtain second order differential equation,

$$\frac{d^2x}{dt^2} = -4x$$

$$\frac{d^2x}{dt^2} + 4x = 0$$

The initial conditions are

$$x(0) = 5 \text{ and } x'(0) = 0$$

$$x''(t) + 4x = 0$$

Applying Kushare integral transform

$$K[x''(t)] + 4K(x) = 0$$

$$v^{2\alpha}s(v) - v^{\alpha+1}x(0) - vx'(0) + 4s(v) = 0$$

$$(v^{2\alpha} + 4)s(v) - 5v^{\alpha+1} - 0 = 0$$

$$(v^{2\alpha} + 4)s(v) = 5v^{\alpha+1}$$

$$s(v) = \frac{5v^{\alpha+1}}{(v^{2\alpha} + 4)}$$

Taking inverse on both side

$$K^{-1}[s(v)] = K^{-1}\left[\frac{5v^{\alpha+1}}{(v^{2\alpha} + 4)}\right]$$

$$x(t) = 5 \cos 2t$$

- The relationship between resistive force of air and the velocity of a freely falling body is given by $dy/dt = g - \alpha v$, where $v(t)$ is the velocity at any time t . Initially the body is at rest.
- **Solution:**

Fig. 2: Freely falling body

- **Solution:** See above figure number 2:
The equation for the motion of the body moving under constant gravitational acceleration (as shown in figure) is

$$\frac{dv}{dt} = g - \gamma v$$

i.e $x' = g - \gamma x$

Applying kushare integral transform on both side

$$K[x'(t)] = gK(1) - \gamma K(x)$$

$$v^\alpha s(v) - vf(0) = g\left(\frac{1}{v^{\alpha-1}}\right) - \gamma s(v)$$

$$v^\alpha s(v) - 0 = g\left(\frac{1}{v^{\alpha-1}}\right) - \gamma s(v)$$

$$v^\alpha s(v) + \gamma s(v) = g\left(\frac{1}{v^{\alpha-1}}\right)$$

$$(v^\alpha + \gamma)s(v) = \frac{g}{v^{\alpha-1}}$$

$$s(v) = \left(\frac{g}{v^{\alpha-1}}\right)\left(\frac{1}{v^\alpha + \gamma}\right)$$

$$s(v) = \left(\frac{g}{v^{\alpha-1}}\right)\left(\frac{1}{\gamma} - \frac{v^\alpha/\gamma}{v^\alpha + \gamma}\right)$$

$$s(v) = \left(\frac{g}{v^{\alpha-1}}\right) \left(\frac{1}{\gamma} - \frac{v^\alpha}{\gamma(v^\alpha + \gamma)}\right)$$

$$s(v) = \left(\frac{g}{\gamma}\right) \left(\frac{1}{v^{\alpha-1}} - \frac{v^\alpha}{(v^{\alpha-1})(v^\alpha + \gamma)}\right)$$

$$s(v) = \left(\frac{g}{\gamma}\right) \left(\frac{1}{v^{\alpha-1}} - \frac{v}{(v^\alpha + \gamma)}\right)$$

Applying inverse on both side

$$K^{-1}[s(v)] = \left(\frac{g}{\gamma}\right) K^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{v^{\alpha-1}} - \frac{v}{(v^\alpha + \gamma)}\right)$$

$$K^{-1}[s(v)] = \frac{g}{\gamma} \left[K^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{v^{\alpha-1}}\right) - K^{-1} \left(\frac{1}{v^\alpha + \gamma}\right) \right]$$

$$v(t) = \frac{g}{\gamma} (1 - e^{-\gamma t})$$

It is required solution.

IV. CONCLUSION

We have successfully used Kushare transform for solving problems occurring in mechanics and obtain solution exactly or very closer to the solutions obtained by another transform.

REFERENCES

- [1.] S. R. Kushare, D. P. Patil and A. M. Takate, The new integral transform, "Kushare transform", International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management , Vol.3, Issue 9, Sept.2021, PP. 1589-1592
- [2.] D. P. Patil and S. S. Khakale, The new integral transforms "Soham transform, International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management, Vol.3, issue 10, Oct. 2021.
- [3.] R. S. Sanap and D. P. Patil, Kushare integral transform for Newton's law of Cooling, International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management vol.4, Issue1, January 2022, PP. 166-170
- [4.] D. P. Patil, P. S. Nikam, S. D. Shirsath and A. T. Aher, kushare transform for solving the problems on growth and decay; journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research, Vol. 9, Issue-4, April 2022, PP h317 – h-323.
- [5.] D. P. Patil, Sawi transform in Bessel functions, Aayushi International Interdisciplinary Research Journal, Special Issue No. 86, PP 171-175.
- [6.] D. P. Patil, Application of Sawi transform of error function for evaluating Improper integrals, Vol. 11, Issue 20 June 2021, PP 41-45 .
- [7.] D. P. Patil , Applications of integral transforms (Laplace and Shehu) in Chemical Sciences , Aayushi International Interdisciplinary Research Journal , Special Issue 88 PP.437-477 .
- [8.] D. P. Patil, Sawi transform and Convolution theorem for initial boundary value problems (Wave equation), Journal of Research and Development , Vol.11 , Issue 14 June 2021, PP. 133-136 .
- [9.] D. P. Patil, Application of Mahgoub transform in parabolic boundary value problems , International Journal of Current Advanced Research , Vol-9, Issue 4(C), April.2020 , PP. 21949-21951.
- [10.] D. P. Patil, Solution of Wave equation by double Laplace and double Sumudu transform , Vidyabharti International Interdisciplinary Research Journal , Special Issue IVCIMS 2021 , Aug 2021 , PP.135-138.
- [11.] D. P. Patil, Dualities between double integral transforms , International Advanced Journal in Science , Engineering and Technology , Vol.7 , Issue 6 , June 2020 , PP.74-82.
- [12.] Dinkar P. Patil, Shweta L. Kandalkar and Nikita D. Gatkal, Applications of Kushare transform in the system of differential equations, International Advanced Research in Science, Engineering and Technology, Vol. 9, Issue 7, July 2022, pp. 192-195.
- [13.] D. P. Patil, Aboodh and Mahgoub transform in boundary Value problems of System of ordinary differential equations, International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, communication and Technology, Vol.6, Issue 1, June 2021, pp. 67-75.
- [14.] D. P. Patil, Double Mahgoub transform for the solution of parabolic boundary value problems, Journal of Engineering Mathematics and Stat , Vol.4 , Issue (2020).
- [15.] D. P. Patil, Comparative Study of Laplace ,Sumudu , Aboodh , Elazki and Mahgoub transform and application in boundary value problems , International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews , Vol.5 , Issue -4 (2018) PP.22-26.
- [16.] D .P. Patil , Y .S. Suryawanshi , M .D. Nehete , Application of Soham transform for solving volterra Integral Equation of first kind , International Advanced Research Journal in Science , Engineering and Technology , Vol.9, Issue 4 (2022) .
- [17.] D. P. Patil, P. D. Shinde and G. K. Tile, Volterra integral equations of first kind by using Anuj transform, International Journal of Advances in

- Engineering and Management, Vol. 4, Issue 5 , May 2022, pp. 917-920.
- [18.] D. P. Patil, Shweta Rathi and Shrutika Rathi, The new integral transform Soham transform for system of differential equations, International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management, Vol. 4, Issue 5 , May 2022, PP. 1675- 1678.
- [19.] D. P. Patil, Shweta Vispute and Gauri Jadhav, Applications of Emad-Sara transform for general solution of telegraph equation, International Advanced Research Journal in Science , Engineering and Technology, Vol. 9, Issue 6, June2022, pp. 127-132.
- [20.] D. P. Patil, K. S. Kandakar and T. V. Zankar, Application of general integral transform of error function for evaluating improper integrals, International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management, Vol. 4, Issue 6, June 2022.
- [21.] Dinkar Patil, Prerana Thakare and Prajakta Patil, A double general integral transform for the solution of parabolic boundary value problems, International Advanced Research in Science, Engineering and Technology, Vol. 9, Issue 6, June 2022, pp. 82-90.
- [22.] D. P. Patil, S. A. Patil and K. J. Patil, Newton's law of cooling by Emad- Falih transform, International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management, Vol. 4, Issue 6, June 2022, pp. 1515-1519.
- [23.] D. P. Patil, D. S. Shirsath and V. S. Gangurde, Application of Soham transform in Newton's law of cooling, International Journal of Research in Engineering and Science, Vol. 10, Issue 6, (2022) pp. 1299- 1303.
- [24.] Dinkar Patil, Areen Fatema Shaikh, Neha More and Jaweria Shaikh, The HY integral transform for handling growth and Decay problems, Journal of Emerging Technology and Innovative Research, Vol. 9, Issue 6, June 2022, pp. f334-f 343.
- [25.] Dinkar Patil, J. P. Gangurde, S. N. Wagh, T. P. Bachhav, Applications of the HY transform for Newton's law of cooling, International Journal of Research and Analytical Reviews, Vol. 9, Issue 2, June 2022, pp. 740-745.
- [26.] D. P. Patil, Sonal Borse and Darshana Kapadi, Applications of Emad-Falih transform for general solution of telegraph equation, International Journal of Advanced Research in Science, Engineering and Technology, Vol. 9, Issue 6, June 2022, pp. 19450-19454.
- [27.] Dinkar P. Patil, Divya S. Patil and Kanchan S. Malunjar, New integral transform, " Double Kushare transform" , IRE Journals, Vol.6, Issue 1, July 2022, pp. 45-52.
- [28.] Dinkar P. Patil, Priti R. Pardeshi, Rizwana A. R. Shaikh and Harshali M. Deshmukh, Applications of Emad Sara transform in handling population growth and decay problems, International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts, Vol. 10, Issue 7, July 2022, pp. a137-a141.
- [29.] D. P. Patil, B. S. Patel and P. S. Khelukar, Applications of Alenzi transform for handling exponential growth and decay problems, International Journal of Research in Engineering and Science, Vol. 10, Issue 7, July 2022, pp. 158-162.
- [30.] D. P. Patil, A. N. Wani and P. D. Thete, Solutions of Growth Decay Problems by "Emad-Falih Transform", International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology, Vol. 7, Issue 7, July 2022, pp. 196-201.
- [31.] Dinkar P. Patil, Vibhavari J. Nikam, Pranjal S. Wagh and Ashwini A. Jaware, Kushare transform of error functions in evaluating improper integrals, International Journal of Emerging Trends and Technology in Computer Science, Vol. 11, Issue 4, July-Aug 2022, pp. 33-38.
- [32.] Dinkar P. Patil, Priyanka S. Wagh, Pratiksha Wagh, Applications of Kushare Transform in Chemical Sciences, International Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology, 2022, Vol 10, Issue 3.
- [33.] Dinkar P. Patil, Prinka S. Wagh, Pratiksha Wagh, Applications of Soham Transform in Chemical Sciences, International Journal of Science, Engineering and Technology, 2022, Vol 10, Issue 3, pp. 1-5.
- [34.] Dinkar P. Patil, Saloni K. Malpani, Prachi N. Shinde, Convolution theorem for Kushare transform and applications in convolution type Volterra integral equations of first kind, International Journal of Scientific Development and Research, Vol. 7 , Issue 7, July 2022, pp. 262-267.
- [35.] Dinkar Patil and Nikhil Raundal, Applications of double general integral transform for solving boundary value problems in partial differential equations, International Advanced Research Journal in Science, Engineering and Technology, Vol. 9, Issue 6, June 2022, pp. 735-739.
- [36.] D. P. Patil, M. S. Derle and N. K. Rahane, On generalized Double rangai integral transform and applications, Stochastic Modeling and Applications, VOL. 26, No.3, January to June special issue 2022 part-8, pp. 533- 545.
- [37.] D. P. Patil, P. S. Nikam and P. D. Shinde; Kushare transform in solving Faltung type Volterra Integro-Differential equation of first kind , International Advanced Research Journal in Science, Engineering and Technology, vol. 8, Issue 10, Oct. 2022,
- [38.] D. P. Patil, K. S. Kandekar and T. V. Zankar; Application of new general integral transform for solving Abel's integral equations, International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific method, vol. 10, Issue 11, Nov.2022, pp. 1477-1487.
- [39.] Dinkar P. Patil, Priti R. Pardeshi and Rizwana A. R. Shaikh, Applications of Kharrat Toma Transform in Handling Population Growth and Decay Problems, Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innative Research, Vol. 9, Issue 11, November 2022, pp. f179-f187.
- [40.] Dinkar P. Patil, Pranjal S. Wagh, Ashwini A. Jaware and Vibhavari J. Nikam; Evaluation of integrals containing Bessel's functions using Kushare transform, International Journal of Emerging Trends

- and Technology in Computer Science, Vol. 11, Issue 6, November- December 2022, pp. 23-28.
- [41.] Dinkar P. Patil, Prerana D. Thakare and Prajakta R. Patil, General Integral Transform for the Solution of Models in Health Sciences, International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology, Vol. 7 , Issue 12, December 2022, pp. 1177- 1183.
- [42.] Dinkar P. Patil, Shrutika D. Rathi and Shweta D. Rathi; Soham Transform for Analysis of Impulsive Response of Mechanical and Electrical Oscillators, International Journal of All Research Education and Scientific Method, Vol. 11, Issue 1, January 2023, pp. 13-20.
- [43.] D. P. Patil, K. J. Patil and S. A. Patil; Applications of Karry-Kalim-Adnan Transformation(KKAT) in Growth and Decay Problems, International Journal of Innovative Research in Technology, Vol. 9, Issue 7, December 2022, pp. 437- 442.
- [44.] Dinkar P. Patil, Yashashri S. Suryawanshi and Mohini D Nehete, Application of Soham transform for solving mathematical models occurring in health science and biotechnology, International Journal of Mathematics, Statistics and Operations Research, Vol. 2, Number 2, 2022, pp. 273-288.